

A critical reading of "COVID-19 Prediction Using Black-Box Based Pearson Correlation Approach"

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Abstract: This paper is a critical reading of a recently published in the journal *Diagnostics* arising from the need to assess the some standards that are required from scientific papers, specially papers dealing with such a sensitive topic as COVID-19 pandemic. This critical review examines the following aspects of the paper: the definition of the research questions, the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for writing, the quality of the methodology, the reporting of result, the adherence to open science principles, and the coherence of the discussion and conclusions with the reported results. We find that the paper is lacking severely in all these aspects, setting a very low standard for publication. We conclude that peer review must pay more attention to the aspects discussed in this paper in order to maintain trust in scientific publications.

Keywords: COVID-19; critical reading; cases; mortality; prediction; correlation, AI generated text

1. Introduction

The declaration of the COVID-19 by the World Health Organization (WHO) in March 2020 has triggered the publication of thousands of papers covering a plethora of aspects of the pandemic, from epidemiology models [?] to vaccine hesitancy management [?] and machine learning for diagnostics [?]. In this context this paper provides a critical reading of the article "COVID-19 Prediction Using Black-Box Based Pearson Correlation Approach" [?] assessing some essential standards of scientific papers, which become more critical in the medical area, and especially when treating the COVID-19 pandemic. This critical reading is by no means a tutorial on how to write a scientific paper, but we provide short motivations for the detected issues.

As a very general introductory comment, we notice that the title contains the expression "Black-Box Based Pearson Correlation Approach". It seems that the authors confuse so called black box modeling approaches, such as Machine Learning (ML) [?], with a traditional correlation measures [?]. Authors in fact report the application of linear regression and Artificial Neural Network for the prediction of cases and mortality in Greece and Israel.

A brief summary of the paper contents and claims is given in order to put the reader in context. The paper claims to compare prediction of COVID-19 cases and deaths in Greece and Israel, providing some signal prediction results by an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and a multivariable linear regression (MLR) in Table 1, and several figures that we will discuss below. It is to note that in the results section the authors are very imprecise about cases, deaths, and whether they refer to Israel or Greece, the only guide is the captions of the figures. The conclusions provided are routine assertions.

2. Methods

In this section we comment the diverse aspects that will be analysed in the paper with a brief explanation and rationale for the analysis. The critical reading process consists in the examination of the salient features of each aspect in the paper under scrutiny highlighting the deviations from good practices found.

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2.1. *ML Methodology*

There is already a widely accepted consensus on the standard methodological elements that must be contemplated in the experimentation with and reporting of ML models [?]. Here are the most relevant for the paper under scrutiny:

1. Definition of the research question that includes the ML models that will be exploited and the meaning of the dependent variables (output) to be predicted, and the motivation for this analysis.
2. Detailed description of the independent (input) variables, including descriptive statistics of the dataset. Feature selection and/or feature extraction processes are also specified here.
3. Detailed description of data pre-processing. Including data cleaning, normalization or scaling of the data and handling of outliers or null values.
4. Detailed description of validation approach with specification of data set partitioning for training, validation, and test. Separation of training and test is critical to avoid double dipping [?] bias in the estimation of generalization results (aka external validation).
5. Definition of the performance measures and experimental design, including the relevant statistical tests used for the analysis of the experimental results and the extraction of conclusions from the study.
6. Exhaustive report of all computational experiment results and discussion relating them to the relevant literature. Many papers include supplementary material when the size of the comprehensive report is excessive.

2.2. *AI writing*

Since the appearance of ChatGPT (<https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>) the issue of the ethically correct use of this AI tool for scientific paper writing has been considered with growing concern [?]. There is an increasing acceptance of its use as an auxiliary tool, some kind of spellchecking on steroids. Some editorial companies, such as Elsevier, are including an AI writing disclosing section in the manuscript submission process. However, it is good practice to check if the submitted paper has been partially or entirely generated by AI writing, as a profilactic measure. Here we have used two tools, ZeroGPT (<https://www.zerogpt.com/>) and turniting (<https://www.turnitin.com>) that provide estimations of the content that is likely to be generated by AI.

2.3. *Result reporting and visualization*

Result report should be consistent with the research question posed, the definition of performance measures, and the experimental design. Table contents should be clear and self-explanatory as much as possible. Graphs and visualization should be intelligible and according to standard expectations. Both tables and figures should be according to the text.

2.4. *Discussion and Conclusions*

The conclusion section of a scientific article is a fundamental aspect, as it serves as the end of the study and summarises the key results and findings. Both discussion and findings should be related to the research question and the experimental design followed.

2.5. *Open science*

Open Science [?] is a movement that aims to make scientific research and its results more accessible, transparent and collaborative. The following are some key principles:

- Open access to research results: papers should be open access to all readers.
- Open access to the data: the data used for the study should be accessible without limitations. This is of special importance when the conclusions of the study may influence policy makers. Specially when high impact policies are potentially harming the people.

- Open access to code: the code should be ready for third party validation of the claimed results. If the code is not functional, the claims of the papers can not be sustained. 87
- Reproducibility: in the case of ML studies, reproducibility encompasses access to the code and the original data in a way that allows to reproduce the claimed results. Non-reproducible studies should not be taken into consideration for policy making. 88
- Open peer review 90
- Ethical conduct of research that includes also ethical paper writing, i.e. no misleading conclusions unsupported by evidence, or the mischievous use of AI tools. 91

3. Results 92

In this section, we provide a detailed report of the results of the critical reading, structured in sections corresponding to the ones identified above. 93

3.1. ML Methodology 94

3.1.1. Research questions 95

The research questions as stated in the abstract and repeated in the introduction are defined as follows: *"The current study aimed to (I) compare the weekly COVID-19 cases between Israel and Greece, (II) compare the monthly COVID-19 mortality cases between Israel and Greece, (III) evaluate and report the influence of the vaccination rate on COVID-19 mortality cases in Israel, and (IV) predict the number of COVID-19 cases in Israel."* Authors claim that this research is highly original, however their review of the literature does not support this claim. Hence it appears that the dependent variables are the number of cases and deaths attributed to COVID-19 in the two countries. However, we do not know if the authors refer to cumulative number of cases or the daily/weekly count of cases. In figure 7 the number of cases look as a cumulative curve, however in figure 8 is not evident which kind of variable are the authors dealing with. For questions (I) and (II) there is no specific measure of comparison between countries in the paper. It is not explained why questions (III) and (IV) are restricted to Israel. 96

Searching in the paper where these research questions have been treated, we do not find any result reporting a comparison between Israel and Greece that would correspond to questions (I) and (II). Table 1 provides some results of ANN and MLR regression, but it appears to be restricted to Israel, though it is not indicated in the caption of the Table, which corresponds to question (IV). Figure 6 seems to obey to question (III), while the other figures do not show any comparison between Israel and Greece. In conclusion, it appears that questions (I) and (II) have been neglected by the authors. 97

3.1.2. Data-set 98

The origins of the dataset are not disclosed. There is only a general reference to the kaggle site, but no information of the original source (like the national statistics institutes of each country). The authors mention over 200.000 COVID-19 case records and 52 independent variables. No explanation is given about the nature of the variables. Are they time series of some kind? No information is provided. Without this information it is not possible to assess the pertinence of the selected modeling methods and results. 99

3.1.3. Data pre-processing 100

In this study, authors normalize the data to a customized range of [0.05,1] without any explanation. This artificial range may introduce some modifications in the results that are not considered. Authors did comment on the need to curate the data, mentioning missing value completion and others, without details. Data manipulation may operate strong changes in the results. 101

3.1.4. Validation 102

It is significant to notice that the validation technique of the predictive methods is not entirely obvious regarding the steps given in the methods section previously. Authors 103

mention 70-30 hold up and 4-fold cross validation processes, but it is not evident which and how it is applied in the computations. No in-depth statistics have been provided for each of these tests in the results tables. Generally, a good practice is showing the standard deviations of the tests that were run in order to better comprehend the results' variability and to increase the validity of the evaluation of the predictive methods. We do not appreciate that any statistical significance test of any performance measure is given.

3.1.5. Experimental design

Authors take some space to describe well known ANN and MLR regression methods, but the description is not complete. For instance, training of the ANN is not commented while other minutiae are described in some detail. The software used for each computational process is not adequately explained, there is some kind of mixture of Matlab, R, and Excel resources, but remain unclear. The title and introduction talk about "black box correlation based approaches" but the correlation only appears explicitly in Table 1 comparing the predicted and actual time series of cases in Israel.

There is no experimental design comparing modeling alternatives that we may found. Authors report comparisons between training and testing results that are of no interest for the reader, who will be interested only on the testing results. Figures 7 to 10 have no interest for the reader that is usually well aware that training and testing results should differ. If the authors want to discuss overfitting, it does not appear in the paper. Figures 9 and 10 are rather difficult to interpret and do not correspond to any conventional experimental design.

There is some confusion in the authors about the meaning of the measures. In several places the authors reported that the two ML models have obtained 94% and 98% accuracy. These values correspond to the R values that appear in the table of model results, i.e. the correlation between predicted and actual time series. Accuracy and correlation are not equivalent concepts. Looking at figures 7 and 8 it is clear that predicted and actual time series follow the same trend, hence the high correlation, however it is clear that the error of prediction is substantial. So the authors are jumping into conclusions that are not well supported by the results.

3.1.6. Results reporting

The reporting of the results consists of one table and ten figures. The table contain single results of regression performance measures, including a correlation R between predicted and actual time series of cases in Israel. There is no corresponding table for mortality results. As explained above there is no statistical significance test of any value reported in the table suggesting that a single run has been made of model adjustment.

Figures 2 to 5 seem to be some kind of descriptive tools. They appear to be irrelevant to answer any of the research questions. Figure captions are completely uninformative of the plot contents. They may be some kind of report on the correlation of variables, but very flawed for the following reasons:

1. Assume that each row contains some correlation values (normalized as percentages) among variables as identified by the color code at the bottom, there is no way to ensure that sum of considered correlation will be 100%. As a cover up it seems that authors place the lacking percentage as some kind of self-correlation (bar segment with the same color as the variable) which highly irregular procedure.
2. The "dependent" variables seem to be the cumulative cases and deaths in Israel and Greece, with a plot for each combination. However the "independent" variables are weekly counts that go up and down while the dependent variables always go up (monotonically increasing). Hence computing the correlation of these time series has no meaning. Despite that, authors report positive correlations in almost all pairs of variables (if our interpretation is correct).
3. For the cases plots (Figures 2 and 4) the independent variables are hospital admissions and intensive care unit (ICU) admissions. These variables are in fact dependent of

the number of cases. In other words, there is a causative link between (weekly) cases and these variables as the cases may become (with some delay) hospital admissions, and the hospital admissions may become ICU admissions. Hence, using them as explicative variables for the (total) cases is senseless.

4. For the deaths plots (Figures 3 and 5) the independent variables are death count variables, which is perfectly senseless. "Total deaths" and "total deaths per million" are perfectly correlated variables, in fact is the same variable except for a scale factor. Same for "new deaths" and "new deaths per million", and "new deaths smoothed" and "new deaths smoothed per million". The correlation between these pairs should be 100%, but the authors report other values!. In any case, only one of the pair should be used in any regression or correlation analysis. Furthermore, computing the correlation between the various death variables that have the same information is perfectly senseless.
5. Similarly, in the cases plots (Figures 2 and 4) "weekly hospital admissions" and "weekly hospital admissions per million" are perfectly colinear, as are "weekly icu admissions" and "weekly icu admissions per million". The values in the plots appear to be completely disconnected from reality.

Figure 6 seems to try to answer question (III) following the interpretation of the plot as correlation coefficients. Authors include an explanatory phrase at the end of section 3.1 that offers a remarkable conclusion "As demonstrated in Figure 6, there was a strong correlation between total vaccinations and total death cases in Israel. The rate of vaccination, therefore, did not influence the mortality rate."

Figure 7 and 8 visualize the comparison between MLR predicted and actual time series of cases for the training and testing data, respectively, without specification of country. It can be appreciated that the predicted and actual time series do not match, so that prediction error should be significantly high but there is no specific statistical test. Figure 7 confirms that the actual cases time series is cumulative. The units of the x-axis and y-axis are not specified (day?, cases?). In Figure 8, the cumulative nature of the cases variable is not so evident, maybe due to some figure rendering effect, may be trying to have a 3D effect. The units of the x-axis and y-axis are not specified (day?, cases?), and a label "total_cases"inthex – axisaddstotheconfusion.

The comparison of ANN training and testing R^2 values with MLR R^2 value (at testing?) provided by Figure 9 has no specific scientific value. Furthermore, the mention in the caption of "clustered" is highly confusing. Authors have not carried out any clustering process. Similarly, the comparison in figure 10 is of little interest and it is not convincingly explained in the text. The x-axis is undefined in this figure, and the y-axis labels are strange. What is the meaning of the numbers 3 and 4 in this axis? The explanation in the text of these figures is meaningless.

3.2. AI writing

The writing of abstract and introduction sections collects many common trivia about the pandemic with little relevance to the actual research question. The application of ZeroGPT over the text of the various sections carried out online (screenshots can be found in [?]) provided the following results:

1. Abstract - 85.9%
2. Introduction - 54.29%
3. Materials and Methods - Data 45.13% - Models 54.82%
4. Application of Results and Discussion - 17.03%
5. Conclusions - 0%

The application of turning tools for AI writing detection resulted in the estimation that 23% of the entire paper was generated by AI. Putting together these results, and the relative lack of coherence in the writing, it seems that much of the writing was done by AI. As far as we know, the journal does not asks for AI writing disclosure at the time of this writing. Other than that, the paper has many awkward expressions such as "Analyzing data

helps determine the navigational and scientific value of the data" in the first paragraph of section 3. 232
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3.3. Discussion and Conclusions 234

Discussion of results is missing. The conclusions section is a collection of uninformative trivialities. However, as pointed above, there is a strong conclusion formulated in regard of figure 6 that has been neglected in the conclusions section. We remind the reader of the literal phrase at the end of section 3.1 "As demonstrated in Figure 6, there was a strong correlation between total vaccinations and total death cases in Israel. The rate of vaccination, therefore, did not influence the mortality rate." It appears that, for some reason, the authors have overlooked this strong conclusion both in the abstract and in the conclusions section. 235
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3.4. Open science 242

Regarding following open science practices, the authors have failed in several aspects. First, they do not reference with precision the data source, giving only the generic url of the Kaggle site, neither give any link to a repository where the exact data version can be retrieved. Furthermore, they do not provide the code used for the computations. Their description of the implementations is confusing, mentioning Matlab, R, and Excel in way that is impossible to know what tool has been used for what result. It appears that figures have been created with Excel. Therefore, the works of the authors are irreproducible. Besides, authors have apparently used AI writing tools without disclosure. 243
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4. Discussion and Conclusions 251

This critical reading paper should have highlighted that very low quality papers can be accepted and published as peer review papers. We think that this is a very critical issue for science today. The role of reviewers and academic editors is paramount to ensure at least formal quality standards of the published papers that may allow a proper scientific discussion over issues of great impact, such as it is everything related to COVID-19 pandemic, which has given a strong shock to all strata of society. A simple search in PubMed with the single term "COVID-19" provides almost 400,000 references in the very short time span since the declaration of the pandemic by the WHO. It is rather evident that a large army of reviewers and academic editors free from conflicts of interest should be levied to face this tsunami of papers, but quality reviewers and academic editors should also consider their own publication track which would wither if they put too much effort and time in reviewing tasks [?]. Without touching the discussion of the demographics of the research community, it is very likely that science and scientific publication is at some critical point, that has been acknowledged for some time [?]. The paper that has been the subject of this critical reading is just another in a huge heap of scientific misinformation [?] arising from careless or compromised publication. If we have to highlight something from this critical reading exercise is the removal of any reference to the conclusions that the authors extract from Figure 6 in their paper in the abstract or the conclusions section of their paper. This is no trivial matter, as many papers in the literature about COVID-19 seem to have followed this pattern. Important and ground breaking but controversial results found by the authors are relegated to supplementary material or left out of discussion. Oftentimes this is due not to the desire or lack of knowledge of the authors. As a conclusion we would ask not only more systematic rigour in the reviewing process, but also the freedom to state clearly the findings of the work, even if this breaks some interests that are spurious to science. 252
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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

ML	Machine Learning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
MLR	Multivariate Linear Regression
ICU	Intensive care unit

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